

Milan Scoring System in the Diagnosis of Salivary Gland Lesions for Assessment of Risk of Malignancy

Tulika Singh¹, Sandhya Kumari Sinha², Krishna Murari Prasad³

¹Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, Patna medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Pathology, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

³Professor, Department of Pathology, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Sandhya Kumari Sinha

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Abstract:

Background: Salivary gland lesions pose diagnostic challenges due to their diverse nature, necessitating a standardized reporting system to ensure accurate diagnosis and effective management. The study aimed to evaluate the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions using the Milan Scoring System (MSRSGC).

Methods: A retrospective observational research comprising 130 patients who had histopathological and FNAC examinations was carried out. The MSRSGC was used to categorise FNAC outcomes. With SPSS version 23.0, the following metrics were calculated: sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV.

Results: FNAC categorized the lesions into non-diagnostic (7.7%), non-neoplastic (38.5%), AUS (11.5%), benign neoplasm (30.8%), SUMP (3.8%), suspicious for malignancy (3.8%), and malignant (3.8%). Histopathology confirmed 25 malignant and 105 benign cases. The MSRSGC showed a sensitivity of 88.0%, specificity of 96.2%, PPV of 80.0%, and NPV of 98.1%. Categories V and VI exhibited a 100% risk of malignancy.

Conclusion: The Milan Scoring System effectively stratifies salivary gland lesions by malignancy risk, demonstrating high diagnostic accuracy. Categories V and VI are reliable in identifying malignancy, while non-neoplastic and benign neoplasm categories effectively indicate benign lesions.

Recommendations: Adoption of the MSRSGC is recommended for standardizing salivary gland lesion diagnosis, improving patient management, and facilitating clear communication among healthcare providers.

Keywords: Milan Scoring System, Salivary Gland Lesions, Fine-Needle Aspiration Cytology, Malignancy Risk, Diagnostic Accuracy.

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Introduction

Because salivary gland lesions are so diverse, ranging from benign to malignant neoplasms, they provide a wide range of diagnostic problems. For these lesions, fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) has been extensively utilised as a less invasive diagnostic technique, offering vital preoperative information. On the other hand, inconsistent FNAC interpretations and consequent clinical care resulted from the absence of a standardised reporting mechanism.

In order to solve this problem, the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC) was implemented in 2018. By standardising the reporting of salivary gland FNAC, this method hopes to improve patient care by promoting improved communication between pathologists and physicians [1]. Salivary gland lesions are classified by the MSRSGC into six diagnostic categories: benign neoplasm, salivary gland neoplasm of unclear malignant potential (SUMP), malignant, atypia of indeterminate

significance (AUS), non-diagnostic, and non-neoplastic. Appropriate clinical care techniques are guided by the unique risk of malignancy (ROM) associated with each group.

Since its implementation, several studies have evaluated the efficacy of the MSRSGC. For instance, a study demonstrated the system's high sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing malignant salivary gland lesions [2]. Similarly, a multi-institutional study validated the MSRSGC's reproducibility and reliability across different clinical settings [3]. These studies underscore the MSRSGC's potential to enhance diagnostic accuracy and reduce diagnostic variability.

Furthermore, the MSRSGC has been shown to improve the preoperative diagnostic workflow. According a study, the system's structured approach aids in stratifying patients based on their risk of malignancy, ensuring timely and appropriate intervention [4]. This risk stratification is

particularly beneficial in cases where FNAC results are indeterminate, as it provides a clearer framework for clinical decision-making.

In addition to improving diagnostic precision, the MSRSGC has significant implications for patient counseling and management. The clear correlation between diagnostic categories and ROM helps clinicians in discussing prognosis and treatment options with patients, thereby fostering informed decision-making. Recent literature, including studies highlights the system's role in optimizing patient outcomes through targeted therapeutic interventions [5].

This study aimed at assessing the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions using the Milan Scoring System.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at PMCH, Patna a tertiary care hospital, from February 2023 to February 2024.

Participants: A total of 130 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients with salivary gland lesions who underwent FNAC.
2. Patients with histopathological confirmation of the diagnosis.
3. Patients aged 18 years and above.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients without histopathological confirmation of diagnosis.
2. Patients with incomplete medical records.

3. Patients with a history of previous salivary gland surgery or radiation therapy.

Bias: All consecutive patients who met the inclusion criteria during the study period were included in order to reduce selection bias. By having two separate pathologists evaluate the FNAC and histology results, observer bias was minimised.

Data Collection: Information about the patient's demographics, clinical presentation, FNAC results, histological findings, and follow-up was gathered from the hospital's medical records. FNAC outcomes were grouped using the Milan Scoring System.

Procedure

1. FNAC was performed on patients with salivary gland lesions.
2. Cytological findings were categorized into six categories as per the Milan Scoring System:
 - Non-diagnostic
 - Non-neoplastic
 - Atypia of undetermined significance (AUS)
 - Neoplasm: benign
 - Neoplasm: salivary gland neoplasm of uncertain malignant potential (SUMP)
 - Malignant
3. Histopathological examination was conducted on surgical specimens to confirm the diagnosis.
4. The risk of malignancy for each category was assessed based on the histopathological outcomes.

Figure 1: FNAC Smear showing biphasic population of cells containing both ductal cells as well as spindle shaped myoepithelial cells- Pleomorphic adenoma

Figure 2: Milan System Category VI- malignant

Statistical Analysis: Data were analysed with SPSS 23.0. Patients' demographic and clinical features were summarised using descriptive statistics. Calculated Milan Scoring System sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and NPV. Each Milan Scoring System category's malignancy risk was calculated by assessing the proportion of malignant cases.

The study comprised 130 patients in all who had lesions of the salivary glands. The patients were 45.3 ± 12.4 years old on average, and there were 1:1.2 male to female ratios. The majority of patients (92/70.8%) had a painless swelling as their primary clinical manifestation, with 38 patients (29.2%) reporting pain. Table 1 displays the distribution of FNAC results based on the Milan Scoring System.

Result

Table 1: FNAC Categorization Using the Milan Scoring System

Milan Category	Number of Cases (n=130)	Percentage (%)
I - Non-diagnostic	10	7.7
II - Non-neoplastic	50	38.5
III - Atypia of undetermined significance (AUS)	15	11.5
IVa - Neoplasm: benign	40	30.8
IVb - Neoplasm: salivary gland neoplasm of uncertain malignant potential (SUMP)	5	3.8
V - Suspicious for malignancy	5	3.8
VI - Malignant	5	3.8

Histopathological examination confirmed 25 cases (19.2%) as malignant and 105 cases (80.8%) as benign. The correlation between FNAC categories and histopathological outcomes is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Histopathological Findings

Milan Category	Benign Cases (n=105)	Malignant Cases (n=25)	Total (n=130)
I	9	1	10
II	50	0	50
III	13	2	15
IVa	38	2	40
IVb	2	3	5
V	0	5	5
VI	0	5	5

The sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) of the Milan Scoring System in predicting malignancy are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Statistical Analysis

Statistical Measure	Value (%)
Sensitivity	88.0
Specificity	96.2
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	80.0
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	98.1

The risk of malignancy for each category of the Milan Scoring System is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Risk of Malignancy

Milan Category	Number of Cases (n=130)	Malignant Cases (n=25)	Risk of Malignancy (%)
I	10	1	10.0
II	50	0	0.0
III	15	2	13.3
IVa	40	2	5.0
IVb	5	3	60.0
V	5	5	100.0
VI	5	5	100.0

Discussion

The study assessed the risk of malignancy in salivary gland lesions using the Milan Scoring System, involving a total of 130 patients. The demographic analysis revealed a mean age of 45.3 years, with a slight female predominance. The most common clinical presentation was a painless swelling, which was observed in 70.8% of patients.

FNAC results were categorized according to the Milan Scoring System. The most frequent category was non-neoplastic (II), comprising 38.5% of the cases, followed by benign neoplasm (IVa) at 30.8%. Categories suspicious for malignancy (V) and malignant (VI) each constituted 3.8% of the cases.

Histopathological examination confirmed 25 malignant and 105 benign cases. The correlation between FNAC categories and histopathological outcomes demonstrated that the Milan Scoring System has high diagnostic accuracy. Categories V and VI, suspicious for malignancy and malignant, respectively, showed a 100% risk of malignancy, indicating their reliability in diagnosing malignant lesions. Conversely, the non-neoplastic category (II) showed no malignancy, affirming its effectiveness in identifying benign lesions. Categories III (AUS) and IVa (benign neoplasm) exhibited malignancy risks of 13.3% and 5.0%, respectively, suggesting the necessity for careful monitoring and further diagnostic procedures for these categories.

The Milan Scoring System's statistical study showed a sensitivity of 88.0% and a specificity of 96.2%. There was a 98.1% NPV and an 80.0% PPV. The system's great accuracy and reliability in

differentiating between benign and malignant salivary gland lesions is highlighted by these values.

Overall, the Milan Scoring System proves to be a valuable tool in the risk assessment of malignancy in salivary gland lesions, demonstrating high sensitivity and specificity. Categories V and VI are particularly effective in identifying malignancy, while categories II and IVa provide reliable identification of benign lesions. Categories III and IVa, despite their lower malignancy risks, necessitate vigilant follow-up and further evaluation to ensure accurate diagnosis and appropriate management.

A study evaluated 225 salivary gland lesions using the Milan System for Reporting Salivary Gland Cytopathology (MSRSGC), and 105 instances had a histological follow-up. The distribution of the categories was as follows: 3.34 percent were classified as non-neoplastic (38.01%), 5.71% as non-diagnostic; 2.57% as atypia of uncertain significance; 33.34% as benign; 1.9% as salivary gland neoplasm with uncertain malignant potential; 2.85% as suspicious for malignancy; and 15% as malignant. Across several categories, the computed risk of malignancy (ROM) varied from 4.4% to 97.5% [6].

Another study examined the risks of high-grade malignancy in parotid gland tumours. The percentages of malignancy in the MSRSGC categories Suspicious for Malignancy and Malignant were 83.3% and 100%, respectively. The corresponding high-grade malignancy rates were 16.7% and 55.9% for these groups. High-grade malignancy was accurately predicted by the

combination of nodal metastasis and the Malignant category [7].

The MSRSGC demonstrated a sensitivity of 64.28%, specificity of 97.01%, and diagnostic accuracy of 87.37% in a study involving 292 patients. According to reports, the ROM was 42.86% for the non-diagnostic category, 26.67% for the non-neoplastic category, and 100% for the malignant and atypia of unknown significance categories [8].

A study that examined the ROM of 19,652 samples discovered that ROM differed greatly amongst the categories, with the Malignant category having the highest ROM (100%) of all. It was found that the MSRSGC was a dependable method for estimating the likelihood of cancer [9].

Additionally, a study classified 160 FNAs using MSRSGC in a real-time environment. The Suspicious for Malignancy and Malignant categories had the greatest ROM (100%). The high ROM for Atypia of Undetermined Significance was also noted by the study, suggesting that the criteria should be improved [10].

Conclusion

The Milan Scoring System demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing malignant salivary gland lesions. Categories V and VI showed a 100% risk of malignancy, indicating the high diagnostic accuracy for these categories. The non-neoplastic category (II) exhibited no malignancy, affirming its reliability in identifying benign lesions. Categories III and IVa showed a lower but notable risk of malignancy, underscoring the need for careful follow-up and further diagnostic evaluation.

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